

Post-Reform Dynamics: Growth Trajectories in The Indian Chemical Sector

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Abstract

The current study evaluates the Total Factor Productivity Growth (TFPG) of the Indian chemical industry in the post-reform era by employing Non-parametric Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). The analysis utilizes the CMIE Prowess Database at the firm level for the period from March 1995 to March 2016. The findings indicate a decline in TFPG from 1.004 in 1995-96 to 0.877 in 2015-16, reflecting a 4.6% decrease, with an average TFPG of 0.954 over the study period. Efficiency change is identified as the primary driver of TFPG, suggesting that inputs are being utilized more effectively, contributing to sustainable growth. The determinant analysis reveals that Advertising and Marketing have a U-shaped impact on TFPG, while Research and Development and Net Exports exert a positive influence. Additionally, these strategic variables are significantly affected by TFPG within the Indian chemical industry. The study proposes several policy measures aimed at enhancing TFPG in this sector.

Key Words: Total factor productivity growth, Manufacturing Sector, Indian Economy, Data Envelopment Analysis, Malmquist Index

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1. Introduction

The development of the manufacturing sector in a structured manner could be instrumental in strengthening the foundations of economies experiencing a downturn in output and employment growth, thereby mitigating the decline in demand. Additionally, considering the increasing significance of the service sector in the global economy and the established inter-sectoral link between services and manufacturing, the growth of the service sector depends on the growth of the manufacturing sector. Enhancing productivity and efficiency in the manufacturing sector may help economies better absorb economic shocks. Numerous studies have emphasized the importance of productivity growth, including works by Tinbergen (1942), Kendrick (1956), Abramovitz (1956), Solow (1957), Denison (1967), and Jorgenson and Grilliches (1967).

There is a conceptual distinction between technological change (TC) and total factor productivity growth (TFPG). Technological change refers to advancements in knowledge and its application to production (through invention, innovation, and diffusion). TFPG, on the other hand, is defined as the growth in output that is not attributed to the growth of inputs. It is a broader concept encompassing TC, technical-efficiency change (TEC), and scale-change. Productivity growth is crucial for increasing output and enhancing the competitiveness of an industry in both domestic and international markets. Scale effects are input-driven; growth driven by increased production factors is subject to diminishing returns and is not sustainable in the long run. Growth stemming from TC and TEC generally results from improvements in knowledge, organizational structures, human resource management, skill development, information technology, and the efficient use of production factors, all of which are more desirable for sustainable growth. Long-term development will benefit more if TFPG is driven by factors other than scale, such as TC and TEC.

The total factor productivity growth (TFPG) of a country's manufacturing sector depends on the TFPG of its various industries. This study examines the TFPG of firms in the Indian chemical industry (ICI) as a case study. The ICI, one of India's oldest manufacturing industries, significantly contributes to the economy, accounting for about 3% of GDP, with USD 60 billion in investment and around 1 million jobs. It ranks 12th globally and 3rd in Asia by volume, producing over 80,000 products. Chemical exports represent 14% of India's total exports, reaching

both developed and developing nations. The INAE study (2011) identifies R&D as a crucial growth driver, with an expenditure of Rs. 7860 Crores in 2008-09. The industry has evolved from a net importer in the 1990s to a net exporter due to increased exports in pharmaceuticals and biotech. The sector is divided into three sub-sectors: basic chemicals, knowledge-intensive chemicals, and specialty chemicals. The basic chemical sector is the largest, while the knowledge-intensive sector emphasizes R&D. The specialty chemical sector, driven by domestic demand and exports, has shown robust growth but faces challenges in R&D access. Both the specialty and knowledge-intensive sectors need R&D for product improvement.

Studies are available on productivity for different Indian industries (Goldar (2014); Ahluwalia (1990), *Deb* and Ray (2014); Ghose and Roy Biswas (2014)). Regarding the factors influencing TFPG, the global literature support the role of the variables like R&D expenditures (Grossman and Helpman (1991), Romer, (1986); Raut and Srinivasan (1993), Cohen and Levinthal (1989), Clark and Griliche (1982), Higon and Anon (2003), Mate-Garcia and Rodriguez Fernandez (2008)), exports (Balassa(1988), Grossman and Helpman (1990a, 1990b, 1991), Barro and Sala-i-Martin, (1995)), imports (Tybout (2000); Grossman and Helpman (1991), Lawrence and Weinstein (2001)), advertisement-expenditures (Syverson (2003); Carod and Blasco (2004)))and marketing-expenditures (Sheth and Sisodia (2002), Kao et al. (2006)) among others.

The present study is significantly different from the earlier in many respects. First of all, as distinct from the previous studies the variations in TFPG of different firms under ICI are estimated employing non-parametric Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), applying the Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI) introduced by Caves, Christensen and Diewert 1982 and using Centre for Monitoring of Indian Economy (CMIE) Prowess data base, for the period 1995-2016. Secondly, the measured MPI is decomposed to separate the contributions of technical-change (TC), technical - efficiency change (TEC) and scale - efficiency change (SEC) using Ray and Desli (1997) methodology. Finally, a second-stage panel regression analysis is resorted to explore the impact of R&D, total exports and imports, advertising-expenditures and marketing expenditures on TFPG. A nexus relationship exists between Indian firms' performance and strategic variables in the post-reform era (Chen & Ibhagui, 2019). Strategic variables like Advertising Intensity (ADV), Marketing Intensity (MKT), R&D Intensity (RD), and Net Export

Intensity (NX) may be endogenous, affecting TFPG and being influenced by TFPG. Few studies have explored these simultaneous relationships. This study addresses this gap by examining the determinants of TFPG using a simultaneous panel model (EC2SLS random-effects IV regression) for TFPG, ADV, MKT, RD, and NX. It is crucial for policy-making to enhance Indian chemical firms' performance.

The rest of the chapter unfolds as follows. Section 2 reports the data source. Section 3 contains the results of estimation of TFPG and its decomposition analysis. Section 4 explains the determinants of TFPG. Section 5 concludes the study along with some policy suggestions to promote TFPG.

2. Data Sources

The sample consists of 223 chemical companies' (firm) data collected from Centre for Monitoring of Indian Economy (CMIE) Prowess database, over the period 1995-1996 to 2015-2016.

The study conceptualizes a 1-output and 5-inputs production technology. The output is the total sales of the firm deflated by the WPI for textiles (base 1993-94 =100). The inputs are: (i) Raw Material inputs (measured in terms of the companies' expenditure on raw materials, stores and spares) deflated by the WPI for manufacturing products (base 1993-94 =100) , (ii) Energy and water Input (measured in terms of the expenditure of the companies for power, fuel and water) deflated by WPI of power & fuel (base 1993-94 =100) , (iii) Labour (measured in terms of wages and salaries of the workers and nominal wage has been deflated by WPI (base 1993-94 = 100), (iv) Land (measured in terms of rent & lease rent paid) and (v) Capital (measured in terms of value of the net fixed assets) deflated by WPI of machinery (base: 1993-94 =100).

3. Empirical Analysis

Table 1 represents summary of means MPI of different firms annually and its decomposition into different components.

Table 1: Malmquist Index Summary of Annual Means of Chemical firms

Year	TEC	TC	SEC	MPI Index (TFPG)
1995-96	1.064	0.943	1.081	1.004
1996-97	0.875	1.042	0.936	0.912
1997-98	0.990	0.902	0.974	0.893

1998-99	1.093	0.911	1.145	0.995
1999-2000	1.262	0.744	1.109	0.939
2000-01	0.972	0.983	1.000	0.955
2001-02	0.933	1.075	0.930	1.003
2002-03	0.984	0.960	1.007	0.945
2003-04	0.977	1.015	0.936	0.992
2004-05	0.966	1.069	0.986	1.033
2005-06	1.147	0.835	1.054	0.958
2006-07	0.923	1.050	1.047	0.969
2007-08	0.922	1.003	0.977	0.925
2008-09	0.997	0.971	1.017	0.968
2009-10	1.108	0.818	0.989	0.907
2010-11	0.906	1.047	0.940	0.949
2011-12	1.113	0.812	1.096	0.904
2012-13	1.125	0.839	1.044	0.944
2013-14	0.900	1.098	0.936	0.988
2014-15	0.760	1.307	0.818	0.993
2015-16	0.957	0.917	0.961	0.877
Grand Mean	0.993	0.961	0.996	0.954

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 1 reveals that TFPG falls from 1.004 in 1995-96 to 0.877 in 2015-16. Mean TFPG is 0.954 indicating that TFPG has declined by 4.6%. The TEC falls from 1.064 in 1995-96 to 0.957 in 2015-16. The mean TEC is 0.993, meaning that TEC has declined by 0.7%. The TC falls from 0.943 in 1995-96 to 0.917 in 2015-16. The mean TC is 0.961, implying that TC falls by 3.9%. The SEC falls from 1.081 in 1995-96 to 0.961 in 2015-16. The mean SEC is 0.996, indicating that SEC falls by 0.4% over the study period. The fall in TEC, TC and SEC lead to overall fall in TFPG during the study period.

Table 2: Mean Growth rate of Efficiency Change, Technical Change, Scale Change and TFPG

Industry	Mean Growth rate (%) of Efficiency Change	Mean Growth rate (%) of Technical Change	Mean Growth rate (%) of Scale Change	Mean Growth rate (%) of TFPG
Chemical	33.71	4.62	5.35	29.89

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 2 shows that the growth rate of efficiency change is the largest contributor of total factor productivity change for chemical industry. This result suggests that efficiency change is contributing the most towards TFPG, implying that the same level of inputs is being efficiently used, as a result of which, the higher amount of output is getting produced which brings about sustainable growth.

4. Determinants of Productivity

A second stage panel regression has been carried out to relate the productivity (TFPG) of Indian manufacturing firms with the strategic variables perused by firms as well as firms' characteristics namely ADV Intensity, MKT Intensity, RD Intensity, Net Export Intensity, Age, Diversification Index, Size and Age of the firm. The explanations for the inclusion of different explanatory variables can be summarized as follows.

Advertising Intensity (ADV):

Advertising, by promoting product substitutability, impacts firm productivity, leading to less productivity variation and higher average productivity in high-substitutability industries. Studies like Luo and Donthu (2005) and Tucker (2008) have explored the effect of advertising expenditure on productivity.

Marketing Intensity (MKT):

Marketing activity, which proxies product differentiation, is increasingly crucial in determining firm productivity. Rust et al. (2004) offer a framework for assessing marketing productivity and highlight its growing importance in enhancing firm performance. Research in marketing performance measurement includes studies by Donthu et al. (2005) and Lukas et al. (2005).

R&D Intensity (RD):

Companies investing in R&D can develop advanced technologies that boost their productivity. Enhanced technical knowledge typically leads to higher output levels, suggesting a positive link between a company's productivity and its R&D efforts. Extensive empirical research supports this relationship, including studies by Clark and Griliche (1982), Dietmar (1994), Kwon and Inui (2003), Higon (2003), Mate-Garcia and Rodriguez-Fernandez (2008), Johansson and Lööf (2008), and Moen and Burchardt (2009).

Net Export Intensity (NX):

When analyzing productivity in Indian manufacturing firms, the roles of exports and imports are crucial. Extensive literature shows that exports generally enhance productivity. Studies by Roberts and Tybout (1997), Clerides et al. (1998), Bernard and Jensen (1999) and Alvarez and Lopez (2005) support this. Imports are also vital, particularly for R&D activities. The World Bank reports (1993, 1997) highlight that imports of foreign technology positively impact productivity. Therefore, understanding the relative impact of exports versus imports on productivity is important, and this study uses net exports (NX) to explore this relationship.

Diversification Index (DIVIND):

DIVIND of a particular industry groups capture the effect of market structure on productivity of the firms. DIVIND is the reciprocal of concentration ratio. The Herfindal Index or Concentration Index is calculated as follows: $H = \sum s_i^2$; where s_i is the market share of the i^{th} firm in the market and N is the number of firms. Some researchers expect a negative relationship between CR and TFPG due to increased competition driving technological advancement, while others anticipate a positive relationship due to benefits of large size and secure markets, with empirical literature offering mixed conclusions [(Katz, 1969); (Kendrick, 1973)].

Age: Debate exists on the effect of firm age on performance: older firms may excel due to experience and established advantages (Stinchcombe, 1965), while younger firms might outperform due to greater flexibility in adapting to change (Marshall, 1920). The present study has divided the sample companies into two groups:

Agedum = 1, if Mean Age of the firm < Grand Mean Age (considering all the firms and all time Points taken together)
= 0, Otherwise

Size:

Productivity varies with firm size, as larger firms benefit from cheaper, higher-quality inputs and economies of scale, leading to better performance compared to smaller firms (Penrose, 1959). The present study divides the sample basis on investment into three groups, based on Investment in plant & machinery or equipment according to MSME Classification:

Smalldum = 1, if mean investment < 5 Cr. Rupees
= 0, otherwise
Mediumdum = 1, if mean investment < 10 Cr. rupees
= 0, otherwise
Largedum = 1, if mean investment > 10 Cr. rupees
= 0, otherwise

To avoid dummy variable trap, Mediumdum has been dropped.

It may be possible that the effect of different explanatory variables may be non-linear in nature. To get this effect, the sole effect of different variables, their square terms and the joint effect of different variables will be incorporated. The effects of the lag value (one year lag) of different strategic variables (i.e. the effects of different strategic variable in the previous period) have also been considered.

Explaining the Factors Influencing TFPG of the Firms

The Results from a Two Stage Least Square Type Approach in a Simultaneous Panel Model are as follows. Proposed model is estimated in a panel set up showing simultaneous relationship among different variables. Significant Factors explaining the total factor productivity growth from a Simultaneous Equation Panel Model: *The TFPG Block*. The estimated TFPG of Indian chemical firms and also the other endogenous variables explaining TFPG corresponding to TFPG block can be visualized below.

Chemical Industry

The estimated TFPG of Indian chemical firms and also the other endogenous

variables explaining the TFPG corresponding to TFPG block can be visualized from Table 3 to Table 7.

Table 3: Factors explaining the total factor productivity growth from a Simultaneous Equation Panel Model: The TFPG Block
Endogenous Variable: TFPG

Independent Variable	Coefficient	z-value	p> z
ADV	-.0115817	-3.33	0.001
(ADV) ²	.0000248	2.36	0.018
ADVlag	.011994	3.48	0.000
MKT	-.00347	-3.47	0.001
(MKT) ²	2.28e-06	1.42	0.154
MKTlag	.0032243	4.85	0.000
NX	8.28e-06	0.52	0.604
(NX) ²	-1.17e-09	-1.19	0.233
NX*RD	7.84e-09	0.36	0.719
DIVIND	-.0044082	-2.41	0.016
Agedum	.0230011	1.40	0.163
Wald chi2 = 72.49			
Prob > chi2 = 0.0000			
Determinants		Marginal effects	
ADV		-0.0098	
MKT		-0.0021	
RD		0.0859	
NX		0.0028	

Source: Author's Calculation

The first equation of TFPG Block: The estimated TFPG relation

Table 3 shows that TFPG is positively related to past ADV and MKT, meaning increased ADV and MKT in the previous period boost current TFPG. For current ADV and MKT, initial effects are negative, but beyond critical values, they positively affect TFPG, indicating a U-relationship. As sample firms' ADV and MKT are below these levels, their effects are currently negative. NX has an inverted U-relationship with TFPG, with positive initial impacts but negative effects beyond a certain level. The combined effect of NX and RD is positive, as RD

enhances NX and vice versa. DIVIND negatively affects TFPG, while Agedum shows younger firms are more productive than older ones.

**Table 4: Factors explaining ADV behaviour from a Simultaneous Equation
Panel Model: The TFPG Block
Endogenous Variable: ADV**

Independent Variable	Coefficient	z-value	p> z
TFPG	6.787432	1.82	0.068
MKT	.1058917	3.96	0.000
(MKT) ²	-.0001244	-1.97	0.048
RD	.0291127	2.58	0.010
(RD) ²	-.0000317	-3.68	0.000
RDlag	.0052767	1.41	0.159
RD*MKT	.0001997	4.21	0.000
NXlag	-.0007402	-1.57	0.117
(NXlag) ²	3.11e-08	1.11	0.268
Wald chi2 = 151.31			
Prob > chi2 = 0.0000			
Determinants		Marginal effects	
TFPG		6.7874	
MKT		0.1099	
RD		0.0312	
NXlag		0.0006	

Source: Author's Calculation

The second equation of TFPG Block: The estimated ADV relation

Table 4 shows that ADV is positively related to current TFPG and previous RD, with increases in both boosting ADV. MKT and RD in the current period have an inverted U-relationship with ADV, with initial positive effects that turn negative beyond a critical level. The joint effect of RD and MKT on ADV is positive, indicating that MKT's impact on ADV depends on RD and vice versa. NX from the previous period has a U-relationship with ADV, with an initial negative effect that becomes positive beyond a critical level, leading to a positive net effect.

**Table 5: Factors explaining MKT behaviour from a Simultaneous Equation
Panel Model: The TFPG Block
Endogenous Variable: MKT**

Independent Variable	Coefficient	z-value	p> z
TFPG	8.750437	1.07	0.284
ADV	.5795459	5.40	0.000
(ADV) ²	-.002213	-5.90	0.000
RD	.7338134	5.31	0.000
(RD) ²	-.0006669	-13.84	0.000
RDlag	.0310864	4.39	0.000
RD*ADV	.0196586	26.96	0.000
NX	-.0033287	-3.70	0.000
(NX) ²	6.44e-07	13.07	0.000
NXlag	-.0005862	-0.62	0.532
(NXlag) ²	5.08e-07	9.57	0.000
Wald chi2 = 3158.57			
Prob > chi2 = 0.0000			
Determinants		Marginal effects	
TFPG		8.7504	
ADV		0.5770	
RD		0.6902	
NX		0.0075	
NXlag		0.0054	

Source: Author's Calculation

The third equation of TFPG Block: The estimated MKT relation

Table 5 shows that MKT is positively related to current TFPG and previous RD, with increases in both boosting MKT. ADV and RD in the current period have an inverted U-relationship with MKT, with initial positive effects that turn negative beyond critical levels. The joint effect of RD and ADV on MKT is positive, indicating that MKT's impact depends on RD and vice versa. NX in both the current and previous periods has a U-relationship with MKT, with initial negative effects turning positive beyond critical levels.

**Table 6: Factors explaining RD behaviour from a Simultaneous Equation Panel
Model: The TFPG Block
Endogenous Variable: RD**

Independent Variable	Coefficient	z-value	p> z
TFPG	1.679948	0.28	0.778
MKT	1.46275	7.14	0.000
(MKT) ²	-.0057302	-10.49	0.000
ADV*MKT	.0064799	0.91	0.361
(ADV*MKT) ²	7.10e-07	4.19	0.000
NX	-.0159259	-4.23	0.000
(NX) ²	2.74e-06	18.41	0.000
NXlag	.0111813	4.48	0.000
Largedum	10.99895	1.21	0.228
Wald chi2 = 1346.12 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000			
Determinants		Marginal effects	
TFPG		1.6799	
ADV		5.1914	
MKT		4.9691	
ADV*MKT		1.2466	
NX		0.0021	

Source: Author's Calculation

The fourth equation of TFPG Block: The estimated RD relation

Table 6 shows that RD is positively associated with current TFPG and previous NX, with increases in these factors boosting current RD practices. MKT in the current period has an inverted U-relationship with RD, showing positive initial effects but negative impacts beyond a critical level. The combined effect of ADV and MKT on RD is positive, indicating that the impact of MKT on RD depends on ADV and vice versa. NX in the current period exhibits a U-relationship with RD, with an initial negative effect that turns positive beyond a critical level, resulting in a positive net impact. Additionally, larger firms engage more in RD, indirectly enhancing TFP.

Table 7: Factors explaining NX behaviour from a Simultaneous Equation Panel Model: The TFPG Block
Endogenous Variable: NX

Independent Variable	Coefficient	z-value	p> z
TFPG	4.690333	3.11	0.002
(TFPG) ²	-.0060303	-2.48	0.013
MKT	11.9363	16.69	0.000
RD	6.372078	10.58	0.000
DIVIND	-13.37001	-2.04	0.041
Wald chi2 = 1062.97			
Prob > chi2 = 0.0000			
Determinants		Marginal effects	
TFPG		4.6781	
MKT		11.9363	
RD		6.3721	

Source: Author's Calculation

The fifth equation of TFPG Block: The estimated NX relation

Table 7 shows that NX is positively related to MKT and RD, with higher levels of both boosting NX. TFPG in the current period has an inverted U-relationship with NX, with an initial positive effect that becomes negative beyond a critical level. As TFPG increases significantly, imports may rise, causing NX to decline past this critical level. DIVIND negatively affects TFPG, meaning that as market share concentrates, NX increases.

5. Conclusion

This paper examines the extent of Total Factor Productivity Growth (TFPG) and its determinants in the Indian chemical industry post-reform. The results show that TFPG fell from 1.004 in 1995-96 to 0.877 in 2015-16, marking a 4.6% decline, with an average of 0.954. Technical Efficiency Change (TEC) dropped from 1.064 to 0.957, a 0.7% decrease, with a mean of 0.993. Technical Change (TC) declined from 0.943 to 0.917, a 3.9% reduction, with an average of 0.961. Scale Efficiency Change (SEC) fell from 1.081 to 0.961, a 0.4% drop, with a mean of 0.996. These declines in TEC, TC, and SEC contributed to the overall decrease in TFPG.

Efficiency change is the primary contributor to TFPG, suggesting that inputs are being used more effectively, leading to sustainable growth.

The analysis reveals that for current Advertising (ADV) and Marketing (MKT), initial impacts are negative, but once these variables exceed critical values, they positively affect TFPG, indicating a U-shaped relationship. Since current ADV and MKT levels are below these thresholds, their effects on TFPG are negative. Research and Development (RD) has a positive marginal effect, suggesting that increased RD boosts TFPG. Net exports show a positive relationship, implying that the benefits of exports surpass the impacts of imports. The marginal effects of TFPG on ADV, MKT, RD, and Net Exports are positive, indicating that improvements in TFPG enhance these factors, further boosting TFPG in the Indian chemical industry.

References

- Abramovitz, M. (1956), "Resource and Output Trends in the United States Since 1870", *American Economic Review*, 46, 5-23.
- Ahluwalia, I.J. (1990), "Productivity trends in Indian industry: concern for the nineties", *Productivity*, 31(1).
- Alvarez, R. and Lopez, R. A. (2005), "Exporting and Performance: Evidence From Chilean Plants", *Canadian Journal of Economics*, 38(4): 1384-1400.
- Balassa, B. (1988), Outward Orientation. In Hollis B. Chenery and T. N. Srinivasan (Eds), *Handbook of Development Economics Vol. II (1645-1690)*, Amsterdam: North-Holland.
- Barro, Robert J., & Sala-I-Martin, Xavier (1995), "Economic growth", New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Bernard, A. B. & Jensen, J. B. (1999), "Exporting and Productivity", NBER , Working Paper Series, Working Paper 7135.
- Carod, A., & Blasco, J.M.S. (2004), "The determinants of entry are not independent of start-up size: Some evidence from Spanish manufacturing", Working Paper No.2072/1775, Department of Economics, University Rovira i Virgili.
- Caves D., Laurits, W., Christensen, R. and W. E. Diewert (1982), "The Economic Theory of Index Numbers and The Measurement of Input, Output and Productivity", *Econometrica*, 50(6): 1393-1414.

- Chen, Y. & Ibhagui, O. W. (2019), "R&D-firm performance nexus: New evidence from NASDAQ listed firms", *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance* 50(2):101009.
- Clark, B.K., & Griliches, Z. (1982), "Productivity growth and R&D at the business level: Results from the PIMS data base" NBER Working Paper No. 916, Cambridge, United States.
- Clerides, S.K., Lach S., & Tybout J.R. (1998), "Is learning by exporting important? Microdynamic evidence from Colombia, Mexico, and Morocco", *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, August: 903-948.
- Cohen W.M., & Levinthal, D.A. (1989), "Innovation and learning: Two faces of R&D", *Economic Journal*, 99: 569-596.
- Deb, A.K and Ray, S. (2014), "Total Factor productivity Growth in Indian Manufacturing: A Biennial Malmquist Analysis of Interstate Data", *Indian Economic Review*, 49(1): 1-25.
- Denison, E. F. (1967), "Why Growth Rates Differ- Post War Experience in Nine Western Countries." The Brooking Institution, Washington DC.
- Dietmar, H. (1994), "R&D and productivity in German manufacturing firms", ZEW Discussion Papers No. 94-01.
- Donthu, N. & Yoo, B. (2005), "The effect of personal cultural orientation on consumer ethnocentrism: evaluations and behaviors of US consumers toward Japanese products", *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 18: 7-44.
- Ghose, A. and Roy Biswas, P. (2014), "Impact of Trade Policy on Manufacturing Productivity in India : Evidence using Nonparametric Approach" in Vinish Kathuria, Rajesh Raj S N, and Kunal Sen (edited) , "Productivity in Indian Manufacturing: Measurements, Methods and Analysis", Routledge India.
- Goldar, B. (2014), "Productivity in Indian Manufacturing in the Post-reform Period: A Review of Studies in Vinish Kathuria, Rajesh Raj S N, and Kunal Sen (edited) , Productivity in Indian Manufacturing : Measurements, Methods and Analysis", Routledge India.
- Grossman, G. & Helpman, E. (1990a), "Comparative advantage and long run growth", *American Economic Review*, 80(4): 796-815.
- Higon, M., & Anon, D. (2003), "Total factor productivity and R&D spillovers", Royal Economic Society Annual Conference 2003 series Paper number 107, Royal Economic Society. Royal Economic Society, St. Andrews,U.K.

- Johansson, B. and Lööf, H. (2008), "Innovation, R&D and Productivity: Assessing alternative Specifications of CDM-Models", CESIS Electronic Working Paper Series, Paper No. 159.
- Jorgenson, D. W. and Z. Griliches (1967), "The Explanation of Productivity Change", *Review of Economic Studies*, 34(3): 249-283.
- Kao, Ling-Jing, Chiu, Chih-Chou, Gilbride, T.J., Greg, T.O., Allenby, M. (2006), "A direct approach to evaluating technical and allocative efficiency in marketing", Fisher College of Business, Ohio State University. Available at www.stat.osu.edu/~amd/papers/Efficiency.pdf
- Katz, M.R. (1969), "Theoretical Foundations of Guidance", *Review of Educational Research*, 39(2): 127-140.
- Kendrick, J. W. (1956), "Productivity Trends: Capital and Labor", *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 38(3), 248-257.
- Kendrick, J. W. (1973), "Postwar Productivity Trends in the United States, 1948-1969", National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.
- Kwon, H. U. and T. Inui. 2003. "R&D and Productivity Growth in Japanese Manufacturing Firms", ESRI Discussion Paper Series No.44, Tokyo.
- Lawrence, R. Z. & David, E. W. (2001), "Trade and Growth: Import Led or Export Led? Evidence from Japan and Korea", In Joseph E. Stiglitz and Shahid Yusuf, eds., *Rethinking the East Asian Miracle*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Lawrence, R. Z., & David, E. W. (2001), "Trade and Growth: Import-led or Export-led? Evidence from Japan and Korea", In J.Stiglitz and S.Yusuf (Eds), *Rethinking the East Asian Miracle*. New York: Oxford University Press for the World Bank.
- Luo, X. and Donthu, N. (2005), "Assessing advertising media spending inefficiencies in generating sales", *Journal of Business Research*, 58(1): 28-36.
- Marshall, A. (1920), *Principles of Economics*. 8th Edition, Macmillan, London.
- Mate-Garcia, J. & Rodriguez-Fernandez, J. (2008), "Productivity and R&D: an econometric evidence from Spanish firm-level data," *Applied Economics, Taylor & Francis Journals*, 40(14): 1827-1837.
- Moen, M.S. and S.M. Burchardt, 2010. R&D and productivity: A firm level investigation of the norwegian manufacturing industry. BI Norwegian School of Management - Master Thesis.
- Nd, (1990b).Trade, innovation and growth. *American Economic Review*, 80(2):

86–91.

- Nd, (1991). *Innovation and growth in the global economy*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.
- Nd. (1997). *The State in a Changing World*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Penrose, E.T. (1959), "The Theory of the Growth of the Firm", Oxford University Press: New York.
- Raut, L.K. and Srinivasan, T.N., (1993), *Theories of Economic Growth: Old and New*, in: Basu et al., eds., *Capital Investment and Development*, (Basil Blackwell, Basingstoke).
- Ray, S. C. and E. Desli (1997), "Productivity Growth, Technical Progress and Efficiency Changes in Industrialized Countries: Comment", *American Economic Review*, 85(5): 1033-1039.
- Roberts, M. J. & Tybout, J. R. (1997), "What Makes Exports Boom?", *Directions In Development*, The World Bank Washington, D.C.
- Romer, P.M. (1986), "Increasing returns and long run growth", *Journal of Public Economies*, 94, Oct: 1002–1037.
- Rust, R.T., Lemon, K.N. & Zeithaml, V. A. (2004), "Return on Marketing: Using Customer Equity To Focus Marketing Strategy", *Journal of Marketing*, 68(1): 109-127.
- Sheth, J.N., & Sisodia, R.S. (1998), "Marketing productivity: Issues and analysis", *Journal of Business Research*.
- Solow, R. M. (1957), "Technical Change and the Aggregate Production Function", *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 39(3): 312-320.
- Stinchcombe, A.L. (1965), *Social Structure and Organizations*. In: March, J.P., Ed., *Handbook of Organizations*, Rand McNally, Chicago, 142-193.
- Syverson, C. (2003), "Product substitutability and Productivity Dispersion", Retrieved from www.nber.org/papers/w10049.
- Tinbergen, J. (1942) *On the Theory of Trend Movements*. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, 1, 511-549.
- Tucker, C. (2008), "Identifying Formal and Informal Influence in Technology Adoption with Network Externalities", *Management Science*, 54(12).
- Tybout, J.R. (2000), "Manufacturing firms in developing countries: How well do they do and why?", *Journal of Economic Literature*, XXXVIII: 11–44.
- World Bank (1993). *The East Asian miracle*. USA: Oxford University Press.